

The Torca Experiment: A model of transdisciplinary project-work

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Abstract

All of Colombia's major cities have at least one higher education centre. However, this does not necessarily entail fair access to education for those living outside these cities' main urban areas. Moreover, financial difficulties and the problems inherent to a long commute are often insurmountable barriers for people who want to study but live in comparatively remote regions. To tackle this issue, the Universidad Nacional de Colombia (UNAL) created a particular admission program (PEAMA) to facilitate access to education in this less-favoured population sector. Since the academic interests of any population will be varied, the UNAL offers selected educational programs through the PEAMA. Thus, professors and lecturers are sent to schools that effectively function as nodes of the UNAL in rural areas to allow students to complete the first four semesters of their program of choice. During the first semester of 2022, 15 people from the rural area of Torca in Bogotá decided to begin their higher education studies through the PEAMA. In total, seven different academic programs were chosen. To allow as many students as possible to complete their programs, a transdisciplinary project-based learning model focused on the particular social problems of the community was designed and implemented for that specific case. Thus, three multidisciplinary groups were created to accommodate the 15 students enrolled in the university through the PEAMA: one for students from the literature and philology programs, one for students of economy, agronomy, and the social sciences, and, finally, one for engineering students. This article discusses the model and the first results obtained.

Keywords: Project-based learning, transdisciplinary, humanitarian education, rural

1 Introduction

In 2007, the Universidad Nacional de Colombia (UNAL) started implementing the PEAMA, a special admissions program designed to facilitate access to education for specific population sectors in the periphery of its areas of influence. Initially, the PEAMA was devised to allow students of the periphery campuses of the university, i.e., those in Arauca, Leticia, San Andrés Islas and San Andrés de Tumaco, to enrol in programs offered only in its major campuses, i.e., those in Bogotá, Medellín, Manizales and Palmira. Thus, the students of the periphery campuses would have the chance to study programs that would otherwise be out of reach for them (Acuerdo 025, 2007).

Students admitted to this program completed their undergraduate degrees in three stages. In the first stage, they took the introductory courses of their program of choice in their place of origin. Then, after their fourth semester of studies, they went to one of the main campuses of the university to continue their studies there. Finally, they returned to their places of origin during their last semester to write a thesis or implement a project focused on their territories.

Due to the positive reception of the program and its favourable impacts on students from the periphery campuses of the university, the PEAMA was extended in 2015 to start offering the same services to people who lived in comparatively remote areas that, nevertheless, fell into the regions of influence of the major campuses of the university (Acuerdo 201, 2015). Since there were no periphery university campuses in those areas, professors and lecturers from its main campuses were sent to some rural schools that would effectively begin to function as nodes of the UNAL. Thus, in 2016, the PEAMA Sumapaz was created to allow the people that lived in Nazareth—about 84 km south of Bogotá, in the lower part of the Sumapaz paramo—to enrol in some of the programs offered at the Bogotá campus of the UNAL (Alcaldía Local de Sumapaz, 2022). At that time, the university provided 60 PEAMA spots, of which 18 were taken. Those students chose the following undergraduate programs: nursing, agricultural engineering, agronomic engineering, veterinary medicine and zootechnics. Later, in 2018, the PEAMA Sumapaz program expanded further to allow students graduating from

several rural schools in Bogotá to study at the UNAL. The number of undergraduate programs that could be chosen was also increased (Resolución 405, 2016; Resolución 908, 2018). Afterwards, during the first semester of 2021, a new node of the university was established for the PEAMA Sumapaz in one of the rural schools of the district of Ciudad Bolívar in Bogotá. Finally, in the first semester of 2022, the newest version of the program was established in the rural sector of Torca, located almost at the city's northern border. In this case, 40 courses were offered for 18 students enrolled in 8 programs: civil engineering, mechanical engineering, mechatronics engineering, agronomic engineering, economics, linguistics, English philology, and French philology. Like all students of the PEAMA Sumapaz, the people that graduated from schools in Torca will remain in their place of origin while they complete the first semesters of their chosen programs. During this period, they will learn the foundational and part of the disciplinary content of their programs through project-based learning (PBL). Afterwards, they will go to the Bogotá campus of the UNAL as regular students.

Unlike the original version of the PEAMA, PEAMA Sumapaz is not entirely dependent on the university budget to run. Indeed, the Secretary of Education of Bogotá agreed with the UNAL to facilitate the access to higher education in the rural sectors of the metropolitan area of the city that they deemed most in need of the program. Thus, the funding for the PEAMA Sumapaz of the UNAL comes from an external entity.

The PBL model used in all iterations of the PEAMA Sumapaz promotes learning through participation in projects that can have concrete impacts in the communities of which students are part. Thus, in Nazareth, for instance, the participants of the project began their studies by deepening their knowledge of their place of origin and by identifying the potential of the region and its inhabitants (Cita Triana et al., 2020; Ordóñez-Ordóñez et al., 2020).

Given the enormous differences between the sectors where PEAMA Sumapaz was implemented, each PBL model used in the program has had to be developed almost from scratch. The form that the transdisciplinary PBL model will take is, thus, different according to the necessities, strengths, weaknesses, and potentials of the stakeholders of the community projects that will be used to teach students the skills that they will need to complete their programs of choice. This article describes the model used in the Torca version of the PEAMA Sumapaz and its first learning outcomes. In addition, some of the open-ended interviews with students carried out to assess the success of the program will be analysed.

2 Torca PBL model

Traditional PBL models use real and concrete problems as the starting point for learning. Problems that may be addressed or solved in a relatively short time are usually chosen for these models. Pioneering universities, such as McMaster in Canada, Maastricht in the Netherlands, New Castel in Australia, and Roskilde in Denmark, have researched and championed PBL models (Neame, 1989; Neufeld et al., 1974; Olsen & Pedersen, 2008; Schmidt, 1989). More recent and less widely spread variations of the PBL methodology choose long-winded projects rather than short problems to drive students to learn. Like many other models, the Aalborg University focus on this type of PBL (Kolmos et al., 2017). The PBL model implemented in Torca described in this paper is also based on project work.

The following statements were used as the PBL principles of the program:

1. Problems must be addressed and solved by a group.
2. Students are responsible for their own learning (self-directed learning).
3. The problems used for learning must be real problems.
4. The problems used for learning must be exemplary.
5. The solutions to these problems are inherently social and must be implemented with the aid of the community.

However, unlike traditional PBL practices (e.g. De Graaff & Kolmos, 2003; Savin-Baden & Major, 2004), the PEAMA students in Torca were comprised of people seeking different learning outcomes since not all of them enrolled on the same undergraduate programs. However, despite this heterogeneity, they were assigned the same problem and project. Thus, students of various engineering branches, the social sciences, and the

agricultural sciences worked side by side on a project that was important to the community to which all of them belonged. Since problems are rarely one-sided, the input from students of very different disciplines, far from hindering processes, often allows for developing more robust solutions.

The transdisciplinary model shown in Figure 1 presents the process followed by everyone involved in the project at Torca.

Figure 1. Torca PBL model.

This model works within a system of three interrelated layers: the social, the academic or institutional, and the student. The first layer is comprised of a community with multiple needs and problems that perhaps could be solved with the aid of higher-education students. The next layer includes the educational organisation and the people working to facilitate students' learning. Finally, students, in their learning process, are the core of formulating and solving the problem affecting the community.

Rather than focusing excessively on the idea of a teacher that transfers some ready-made knowledge to passive students, the role of teachers and other academic staff in the PBL implemented in Torca was to facilitate learning. Indeed, by making the concept of "educator" more flexible, four education-facilitation roles were created for the program. The first kind of facilitator resembles more or less a teacher of a subject in a regular classroom. These facilitators are responsible for concrete courses of the undergraduate programs that the students choose, but their most important task is to encourage students to come up with their answers. The second kind of facilitator is a transversal facilitator who supports the project according to planning, management, and group needs. In addition, they help in the development of soft teamwork skills. The third facilitator is the project chancellor, a person hired by the university to facilitate the exchange between the social and institutional layers. Moreover, the chancellor helps students, other facilitators, and the community to understand, on an academic level, the problems they will be working with. Furthermore, the chancellor works actively to keep the project on its track, i.e., they make sure that students do not get carried away by secondary problems while they work towards completing the project. Finally, the fourth kind of facilitator oversees bringing the literacy or drawing skills of the students to the levels necessary for them to successfully achieve the intended learning outcomes (ILOs) of their program of choice.

Naturally, even though the PBL method dictates that a common problem must be solved by all of the participants of the project, each study program has its own particular ILOs. Thus, to aid students in achieving the ILOs of the program that they chose, the general group of the Torca students was divided into smaller groups—according to the similarity of the contents and skills that they must learn—for some of the activities

that they partake in their day-to-day academic formation. Whether the students achieve these ILOs was determined on a case-by-case basis by a group of facilitators whose input weighed according to their involvement with each particular student. To do this, they assessed the material or immaterial artefacts produced by the students during the development of the project.

Given their importance to the whole process, all the relevant ILOs were explained to the students and the chancellor at the beginning of the project. This, on the one hand, served as a guideline for students during the problem-formulation stage of the project, and, on the other hand, allowed the chancellor to formulate his interpretation of the problems of the community in terms that would be useful for the students to develop the skills necessary for completing their programs.

The solution will produce a report with a material or immaterial product during the problem's development. For example, the product could be the specific outcome that students would use to learn in some or all subjects. In this case, each teacher involved must review the project to assess the achievement of the result of their matter. Consequently, they award the respective grade. On the other hand, the general project allows the evaluation of the transversal skills of the students.

Torca's model also uses subjects that are not part of the project due to their high content of propositional knowledge, such as basic mathematics, principles of chemistry, and computer programming. That cases have lectures and sessions with active learning.

3 Method

The students of the Torca experience went into three groups for the project work, considering that all the subjects involved in some projects to get more balance (Table 1). However, Philology and Linguistics had a group composed of 3 students for a need previously identified as relevant to these careers concerning the school radio station.

Table 1 Project groups for the Torca Model

Name	Curriculum	Project Theme
Student 1	Mechanical Engineering	Reactivation of a scholar greenhouse
Student 2	Civil Engineering	
Student 3	Civil Engineering	
Student 4	Economics	
Student 5	Mechatronic Engineering	
Student 6	Mechatronic Engineering	Solid waste management at the Nuevo Horizonte school
Student 7	Economics	
Student 8	Civil engineering	
Student 9	Agronomic Engineering	
Student 10	Mechanical Engineering	
Student 11	Mechanical Engineering	School Radio Station
Student 12	Philology and Language	
Student 13	Philology and Language	
Student 14	Linguistics	

Students analysed needs during the first six weeks of the project. Identifying the problem is essential that the problem address social needs, but not a pre-established solution.

After the first six weeks of model development, all of them, 14/14 students answered an open-ended interview by the project group. The interviews lasted around 45 minutes for the first two table groups and 21 minutes for the third group. The following research question: Have they found learning of the subjects during the formulation of the problem? Have they managed to identify the project work with the learning outcomes?

4 Results and discussion

The interviews were conducted in Spanish, transcribed verbatim, and analysed contextually. The PBL learning model has shown favourable results in student learning. However, they generally stated that they had difficulties formulating the problem.

During the formulation stage of the problem, the students have managed to understand concepts with the project tools on topic explanations given by the teachers. In this regard, one of the students stated:

"I believe that each subject gives us tools to be able to continue, and one no longer feels so lost concerning the first problem. It no longer feels like that. I don't know how to say it, like that emptiness, well, you can see, you can see a big difference. We picked up things more easily than before starting something before. It was like something. We were lost. So, they have given us excellent tools that are already helping us understand the things they, for example, explain". A Student translated from Spanish.

Despite achieving learning, there was significant difficulty defining the problem during the first six weeks of project work, representing about 40% of the time to carry out the project. The definition of the problem begins with the identification of the needs. Then students analyse it for a possible solution and the relevance to the learning results of the subjects and end with the declaration of research questions and objectives. From this analysis, teachers qualitatively observe if, with that analysis, the students will meet the ILOs by subject. That is the most crucial thing in the development of the project.

The most significant difficulties arose in formulating the objectives during the process. The learning model expected difficulties with problem identification and dilemmas to produce some transformative learning. Several reasons mainly explain it:

- The subject facilitators (Professors) promoted a solution that favoured the application of the theory of that subject, and that intention was generalised to all the group members.
- The Chancellor oriented the project toward the primary need identified.
- Students wanted to develop their solutions to the problem.

The different points of view of the teachers as facilitators caused a certain degree of uncertainty in the students. However, it would foster reflection and argumentation and recognise some topics' lack of depth learning.

"But it is that, for example, the tutoring. It is that they try to lead us along a path with a social stigma that does not bother us. It is as if we end up choosing that idea. Then another teacher comes with another idea, and we believe that idea. So, what happens is that we still don't have things very clear and well. After comes the other, by another side, that we had arrived. It is from one side to the other, and we get a little lost, and of course, since we don't understand things well, then on that side, it is as if they drag us to like their ideas and ideas." A Student translated from Spanish

Many different points of view in identifying the community's needs and how to approach the solution happened, but it seemed to favour a change in the ways students learn. When students come from environments where what the teacher says is done, finding several teachers saying such different things about the same thing produces uncertainty; this setting facilitates reflection (c.f. Rogers, 1951).

"If what Luis says is true, seeing too many points of view. Each one of them...As if he wants to direct us to his thinks or the place of his eyes. He makes us contradict ourselves. Perhaps, if not, we have changed the question." A Student translated from Spanish

This process took six weeks to work and not five as initially expected. However, there were times when the teachers also thought about the inefficiency and lack of clarity in the solution, encouraging behaviourist practices in them, as they manifested in several teacher meetings.

However, the students managed to move forward, understanding that a transformation in their way of thinking about one subject, from traditional teacher centred to student centred with PBL. Traditional local schools are behaviourist. In this regard, a student stated:

“That is called critical thinking, making a significant decision. That is why it makes it necessary, and that is why we have advanced so much. We put both decisions. For example, in each class, we change. Still, today we achieve that it will not modify. This situation occurs when the teacher tries to change the problem, but the students have learned to argue their point of view facing the problem.”
A Student translated from Spanish

Regarding the role of the reading, writing, and drawing facilitator, the students affirmed that they had received the support, and it has been helpful for the formulation of the problem. Reading and writing usually are difficult for students. However, Drawing is an engineering subject that often has an excessive workload in engineering programs. Nevertheless, the students seem to have connected with the other subjects. When asked about it, they stated:

“As we have been in the introduction, they have put us as terms, all those things, plates, plates that are worked freehand, plate in a cube, yes as the terms, as the line types.” A Student translated from Spanish.

The chancellor has been an element with a high degree of influence in the initial part of the project's development. However, his interventions with the students have caused conflict with the other teachers. The students stated there was a contradiction between what he said and the teachers, with a mistaken perception of disorganisation. According to the students' backgrounds, it is better to follow pre-established class schedules with well-defined projects, but not with the responsibility carried out by PBL.

“Well, we have the topic and the problem question. The subject from auditory pedagogical strategies, but we had it as inefficient- Then, talking with teacher Anonymous, he told us that the word insufficient was better. Insufficient auditory pedagogical approaches remained in the Torca institution. The situation is this. There are not enough auditory pedagogical strategies in the school that promote the participation of the members of the educational community, as well as the development of listening and speaking skills in students. Now on Thursday, we will have a class with a teacher who will define that well for us to see if we can leave it or change it for something else.” A Student translated from Spanish

As the previous text marks, at the beginning of the projects, the Chancellor proposed thematic solutions on details that the students did not take as a recommendation for reflection but as a suggestion that would later be transferred to the other facilitating teachers, causing conflicts between them.

5 Conclusion and perspectives

The article described Torca's transdisciplinary model and its first results in student learning outcomes during the problem formulation stage, showing that the model is viable and produces learning but needs minor adjustments. Since the model involving students, professors, facilitators, chancellor, and the community is transdisciplinary.

Although the students managed to define the problem and stated that they are learning, the formulation of the problem occurs in six weeks, which looks pretty long. It is mainly due to various disciplines and their concepts in identifying issues. Also, the need to link problems with ILOs caused some difficulties.

Difficulties incorporating many viewpoints seemed to foster students' critical thinking and argumentation. Finally, the students found a problem and its objectives that appropriately fit everyone to the subjects. However, until the end of the semester, they will show the deep of their learning.

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